

Online Repository 1: Phenotyping of immediate drug hypersensitivity reactions †

	At least one of these symptom must be Present	None of these symptoms must be present	These unspecific symptoms may be included in all reaction phenotypes
Type-1	Pruritus, urticaria, angioedema, nasal congestion, sneezing, wheezing, cough, throat tightness and tongue swelling	Cytokine-release symptoms	Flushing, warmth, erythema, unspecific rashes
Cytokine-release	Chest pain, back pain, headache, rigor, other pain, chills and fever	Type-1 symptoms	Dyspnea, oxygen desaturation, chest tightness
Mixed-type	At least one type-1 symptom and At least one cytokine-release symptoms		Tachycardia, presyncope, syncope, hypertension, hypotension Nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, bloating, reflux
Either type	Unspecific symptoms	Type-1 symptoms and Cytokine-release symptoms	Numbness, weakness, seizures, unusual taste, diaphoresis

† This phenotyping systems was first published by Jared Silver et al.

Silver J, Garcia-Neuer M, Lynch DM, Pasaoglu G, Sloane DE, Castells M. Endophenotyping Oxaliplatin Hypersensitivity: Personalizing Desensitization to the Atypical Platin. *J Allergy Clin Immunol Pract.* May 2020;8(5):1668-1680.e2. doi:10.1016/j.jaip.2020.02.013

Supplementary information of "Hypersensitivity to biologics used in the treatment of inflammatory disorders: allergy interventions and outcomes" to be published in *Clinical & Experimental Allergy*.